

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF INTEGRAL COMPOSITE T-JOINTS UNDER MIXED MODE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel test fixture for application oriented mixed-mode loading of composite T-joints where the force acts under a constant angle with respect to the T-joint's base. Furthermore experimental data of glass fibre composite T-joints under angled mixed-mode and pull-off loading is presented for two different deltoid radii. After a short introduction the specimen manufacturing process as well as the experimental set up is described. Finally the failure phenomenology of mixed-mode loaded specimen is presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the Collaborative Research Centre 880 (SFB 880) the fundamentals of active high-lift for environmentally friendly future transport aircraft are developed. Research by Burnazzi et al [1]. shows the effectiveness of a Coanda-type flap in combination with a contour variable nose (droop-nose) improving the maximum lift as well as the stall angle of attack. Developing a droop-nose whose skin is able to bear the resulting stains in droop configuration while keeping the target shape is of central importance. The design of the droop-nose skin is described by Schmitz and Horst [6]. It uses a central glass fibre laminate surrounded by embedded discrete composite bundles oriented in span-wise direction in an elastic foundation. In order to influence the drooped shape as little as possible, integrally designed T-joints made of glass fibre composite material as load bearing flexible hinges are of great interest and are the focus of this work. The integral design embeds the joint's base into the loaded structure and thereby eliminates the risk of delamination at the ply run outs at the joint's base and reduces the disturbance of the morphing skin during loading compared to bonded joints/stiffeners. The T-joint's deltoid region is of circular shape to increase the T-joint's strength as suggested in research by Cope and Pipes [3] and Panigrahi and Pradhan [5].

Figure 1: Principle sketch of test specimen loading with clamped dimensions and marked displacement evaluation point (DEP).

Figure 2: Manufacturing process

T-joints are imperative for various structures used in aerospace, ships, automotive and other fields to either connect, stiffen or in this particular case as loading hinges. Research so far focused either on tensile or bending testing even though a combined mixed-mode loadcase is far more common in structural application. Finite element models of mixed-mode loading, where the load acts with a constant angle with respect to the T-joint's base, have been numerically investigated whilst no experimental data have been published so far [2]. Figure 1 shows a principle sketch of a mixed-mode loaded T-joint with the resulting deformation while keeping the force angle constant.

Damage onset prediction and the corresponding failure phenomenology in T-joints have been a topic in several publications (e.g. [4]) and is well described for bending or tensile loading. The following work introduces a test fixture which allows application oriented mixed-mode loading of T-joints and provides a set of experimental data for specimens with two different deltoid radii of 4 mm and 6 mm tested under 30° angled mixed-mode as well as 0° pull-off loading. Furthermore, the recorded failure phenomenology for mixed-mode loaded T-joints is presented. The specimen's clamped dimensions are given in Figure 1. Also the displacement evaluation point (DEP), where the specimen's deformations are evaluated, is marked.

2 MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

The T-joints are manufactured from unidirectional E-glass-fibres pre-impregnated with Hexcel's HexPly 913[®] epoxy matrix in a 125° autoclave process according to the manufacturers' data sheet. The material properties are summarized in Table 1. An integral T-joint design was chosen where the outer four surface plies of the base are used for the web which results in an unsymmetrical layup for the web. In total, the layup of the base is $[0, -30, 30, 0, -45, 45, 0, 90]_S$ so that the web's layup results to $[0, -30, 30, 0, 0, -30, 30, 0]$ and the deltoid is filled with 90° prepreg. In order to reduce manufacturing defects a maximum of four plies are stacked and pre-compacted in a vacuum bag for 20 min before final assembly. Two polished aluminium blocks with the desired radii on one edge are used as cavity. Figure 2 shows selected photos of the manufacturing process. After the integral web plies are draped around the aluminium cavities, the 90° deltoid is fitted to the radius and redundant material is cut off (Figure 2a). Merging the two aluminium cavities and draping the base plies on top finishes the T-joints assembly.

After curing, specimen with a nominal width of 20 mm are cut with a diamond bladed machine saw and the specimen cutting edges are wet sanded with a grain size of 18 μm to remove any defects caused by the diamond blade. Figure 3 shows the finished specimen with close ups of the deltoid region.

GFRP HexPly 913 [®]		
E_m	3390	MPa
ν_m	0.380	–
E_f	82800	MPa
ν_{12}	0.230	–
V_f	55.5	%

Table 1: Material properties of HexPly 913[®] prepreg; subscripts $()_m$ for the epoxy matrix and $()_f$ for the E-glass-fiber.

Figure 3: Finished cut and polished specimen (radius R = 6 mm)

3 EXPERIMENTS

The aim of the experimental investigation is to obtain realistic results to validate future finite element models. The mixed-mode loadcase is a common loadcase in a variety of composite structures and easily modelled in FEA. However, a realistic test set up which keeps the loading angle constant with respect to the T-joints base and allows testing of flexible T-joints without adding constraint forces has not been described in the literature yet and no experimental results have been published so far.

3.1 Test Fixture

A special test fixture, which allows these testing conditions, was designed and constructed. A sketch and photograph of the test fixture are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5 with the acting forces and the resulting movement. Special precision rail guides are used for the linear tracking of the T-joint's base and glide bearings for a smooth rotation of the clamping axle to ensure the correct force angle during tensile loading.

Figure 4: Sketch of test fixture.

Due to some rotational friction of the glide bearings a frictional moment M_f is created. A counteracting moment M_c can be generated by moving the specimen center out of the rotational axis of the bearing. The magnitude of the counteracting moment is controlled by the space x between the rotational axis and the specimens center. The frictional moment M_f is calculated using the friction coefficient μ , the bearing diameter d and the acting bearing force F as

$$M_f = \frac{\mu F d}{2}. \quad (1)$$

The counteracting moment

$$M_c = Fx \quad (2)$$

has to be of equal magnitude to counteract the bearings friction. Given the eq. (1) and (2) the necessary space x can be obtained.

3.2 Test Setup

All measurements have been conducted on a universal testing machine equipped with a 5000 N load-cell and the displacement in loading direction is measured using the machine displacement sensor. Furthermore the test fixture is equipped with an inductive displacement transducer to determine the repositioning of the rail guides and a rotation angle sensor. A high speed microscope with external lighting is used to record the damage onset of the specimen's deltoid region during loading. Figure 5 shows a picture of the complete test setup. The specimens are loaded with 3 mm/min and unloaded directly after final failure.

Figure 5: Photography of the experimental test set-up with acting force (white) and resulting movement (red).

4 RESULTES AND DISCUSSION

An exemplary 30° mixed-mode tensile loading until final failure of a T-joint specimen is illustrated in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The corresponding pictures of the high speed camera are shown in Figure 8. It can be stated that each delamination causes a distinct force flux drop at final failure (Figure 6a) whilst the potentially forming micro cracks are not detectable in the force signal. The slowly rising slope of the force flux at the beginning of the experiment is dominated by bending and is characterised with a high change of the web's angle with respect to the base (Figure 6b). With further loading the web's angle gets closer to the loading angle which quickly rises the force flux.

The resulting 30° mixed-mode loading displacements of the DEP are illustrated in Figure 7. Herein, the increasing u_z displacement in the beginning of the slope is presumably caused by settling effects of the axle in the glide bearing since no pre-force is used during the experiments. The following decline results from the increasing web's angle by following a semi-circular path. This motion is also displayed by the u_x displacement whose initial slope decreases with higher force flux because of the approximation of the loading angle and the web's angle.

Figure 6: Force flux against global displacement (a) and angle against force flux (b) of specimen HG_TR4_1.

Figure 7: T-joint web displacement at DEP against force flux of 30° mixed mode loaded specimen HG_TR4_1.

Figure 8 shows the typical phenomenology of a mixed-mode loaded specimen. During testing all mixed-mode loaded specimens regardless of the deltoid radius sizes have formed cracks prior to delamination. Most mixed-mode loaded specimens only show delamination within the tensile loaded radius after unloading. Thus, it can be concluded that potential delamination on the other radius is due to load redistribution and a secondary failure. In contrast, the 0° pull-off specimens show no damage prior to final failure due to delamination within both radii. Delamination of the mixed-mode loaded specimen is observed to occur either stepwise (Figure 8) or global with final failure. No stepwise delamination growth is observed during tensile loading of the 0° pull-off specimen.

Table 2 summarizes the experimental results. Comparing the 30° mixed-mode loaded specimen shows that an increase in deltoid radius increases the force flux at the appearance of the first defect and final failure by 66.4% and 57.2%. Besides that it shows the influence of loading angle comparing the HG_TR6 loaded specimen where the final failure of the 0° loaded specimens is 2.4 times higher than of the 30° mixed-mode loaded specimens.

Specimens	Number of specimen	Deltoid radius (mm)	Loading angle	First defect (N/mm)	Final failure (N/mm)
HG_TR6	7	6	0°	91.9 (±7.0)	91.9 (±7.0)
HG_TR6	6	6	30°	27.3 (±4.7)	38.2 (±5.8)
HG_TR4	10	4	30°	16.4 (±2.6)	24.3 (±3.5)

Table 2: Comparison of the first defect- and failure force fluxes of the tested specimen.

Figure 8: Exemplary phenomenology of progressive failure during loading of a HG_TR4 specimen with a loading angle of 30°.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The presented work describes a novel test fixture for application orientated angled mixed-mode loading of T-joints. It is shown that the test fixture transfers the mixed-mode loadcase as desired by keeping the force angle constant with respect to the T-joint's base. First experimental results of integrally manufactured T-joints are presented and the different failure phenomenologies are described. Future investigations include finite element modelling of the problem in order to predict damage initiation for application purposes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Burnazzi, M.; Radespiel, R. (2014): Design and Analysis of a Droop Nose for Coanda Flap Applications. In: *Journal of Aircraft* 51 (5), S. 1567–1579. DOI: 10.2514/1.C032434.
- [2] Chen, J.; Fox, D. (2012): Numerical investigation into multi-delamination failure of composite T-piece specimens under mixed mode loading using a modified cohesive model. In: *Composite Structures* 94 (6), S. 2010–2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2011.12.030.
- [3] Cope, R. D.; Pipes, R. B. (1982): Design of the composite spar-wingskin joint. In: *Composites* 13 (1), S. 47–53. DOI: 10.1016/0010-4361(82)90170-7.
- [4] Hélénon, F.; Wisnom, M. R.; Hallett, S. R.; Trask, R. S. (2012): Numerical investigation into failure of laminated composite T-piece specimens under tensile loading. In: *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 43 (7), S. 1017–1027. DOI: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2012.02.010.
- [5] Panigrahi, S. K.; Pradhan, B. (2008): Development of Load Coupler Profiles of Spar Wingskin Joints with Improved Performance for Integral Structural Construction of Aircraft Wings. In: *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites* 28 (6), S. 657–673. DOI: 10.1177/0731684407086594.
- [6] Schmitz, A.; Horst, P. (2015): Buckling of multiple discrete composite bundles in the elastomeric foundation of a curvature-morphing skin. In: *Composite Structures* 134, S. 1014–1023. DOI: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.09.004.